

Consortium of European Research Libraries

Newsletter 2 December 2000

For contact details see: <http://www.cerl.org/>

New files on the HPB

SB16

The latest addition to the HPB database is the Svensk bibliografi 1600-1699 (SB16). The records are the result of a retroconversion project carried out in Kungliga biblioteket 1997 based on Isak Collijn, Sveriges bibliografi. 1600-talet. Uppsala 1942-44, 1946 (Vol. 1-2). It contains just over 6,000 records.

The bibliography covers publications by Swedish authors, regardless of printing place and publications printed in Sweden. The exclusions, however, are many, and not always consistently applied, but newspapers and dissertations (that is academic, synodal or school dissertations), legislative print, birthday, wedding and funeral verses, other ephemera and war bulletins are excluded. The Swedish language is represented in over 3,000 records, of the others more than 2,400 record publications in Latin. Greek is represented in a little more than 100 records, and the same goes for Finnish. There are about 450 records for German material. Other vernacular languages are represented in smaller numbers.

The bibliography brings together headings of many libraries in Sweden and in the rest of Europe. The primary basis, however, is the collection in Kungliga Biblioteket, Stockholm. For more information on this file, please see <http://www.cerl.org/hpb/sb16desc.htm>.

In progress

Work on file loading is progressing, and three more files are with RLG awaiting loading:

- c. 4,100 records from the National Library of Russia, St Petersburg (to be followed by regular annual updates)
- c. 25,000 Short-Title records from the *Cathedral Libraries Catalogue, Books printed on the Continent of Europe before 1701 in the Libraries of the Anglican Cathedrals of England and Wales* (no updates)
- c. 38,500 records from the University of London Libraries, London

New e-mail addresses

Please note new e-mail addresses for:

Dr A. Matheson	Ann.Matheson@cerl.org or A.Matheson@tinyworld.co.uk
Dr L. Hellinga	L.Hellinga@cerl.org
Drs M. Lefferts	Marian.Lefferts@cerl.org
A.G. Curwen	Tony.Curwen@cerl.org

These e-mail addresses can be used with immediate effect. All e-mails sent to the old bluk addresses will be forwarded to the new cerl.org addresses at least until the end of February 2001.

UNIMARC output

Conversion specification

In February 2000 Joe Altimus (RLG) completed the work on the RLIN/MARC21 to UNIMARC conversion specification. CERL members have asked whether they would be allowed to use this specification in their own institutions. The Executive Committee agreed the following:

The conversion is available, free of charge, to CERL members, on the condition that this conversion is not passed on to third parties. This specification may not be commercially exploited.

Please note:

- This is not a generic MARC21 to UNIMARC conversion specification.
- The conversion details how UNIMARC format output can be provided for records in the RLIN HPB database. The specification treats all fields defined for HPB, whether they have been used or not, in order to be a comprehensive statement of export requirements.
- The intent in this specification is to include sufficient information about the RLIN HPB file and the UNIMARC format in order to explain the processing rules for HPB fields and character sets.
- CERL cannot undertake any responsibility for conversions developed on the basis of this conversion specification.

Members wishing to receive a copy of this conversion specification should contact CERL's Executive Manager (e-mail address below).

UNIMARC downloading

We are very pleased to announce that the ZedMARC conversion box is now operational. ZedMARC provides on on-the-fly conversion of RLIN/MARC21 to UNIMARC, and ensures that CERL members may download records in UNIMARC. Institutions that wish to make use of this facility should contact the Executive Manager (e-mail address below).

CERL Thesaurus file

RLG have examined the thesaurus prototype (<http://www.cerl.org/thesaur/thesaur.htm>), and are willing and able to integrate the proposed thesaurus file with the HPB database to ensure assisted searching on place and personal names in the HPB database. RLG will begin work on the integration of thesaurus file and HPB in June 2001.

This timetable will give the Data Conversion Group, Göttingen, the opportunity to expand the current place name thesaurus prototype. Data will be derived from CERL members' files, as well as the Getty Thesaurus of Geographic names, Cathedral Libraries' Names of printing towns, and the Association of College and Research Libraries' Latin place names in the imprints of books.

Information for the personal names' Thesaurus file will be extracted from CERL members' files, the printer files of EDIT16, the Koninklijke Bibliotheek Den Haag, and the Bibliothèque nationale de France, as well as the Personennamen Datei of the DDB.

Organisational news

Ann Matheson

New Chair

At the Full Members' meeting in Padua CERL members unanimously elected its new Chair: Dr Ann Matheson, formerly of the National Library of Scotland, Edinburgh. Members, committees and London management all greatly look forward to continue to work closely with her in this new function.

The meeting said their farewells to the parting Chair, Dr Mike Smethurst, with words of praise for his vision and his excellent chairmanship. Dr Smethurst thanked all he had worked with over the years, and said that he hoped to continue to follow CERL's progress closely.

CERL Charging structure 2000-2001

All access to and use of the HPB and ESTC files is **free** for CERL members - there will be no charge in 2000-2001.

For access to the RLIN Bibliographical database, the CURL Union Catalogue, the Deutsche Bibliothek database, and the National Library of Australia Catalogue all CERL members are given 200 free searches in total. After that a charge of **\$0.80 per search** applies. For information on what constitutes a search, please consult: <http://www.rlg.org/whatsrch.html>

Blackwell's Table of Contents file

RLG will discontinue providing access to the Blackwell's Table of Contents file on December 31, 2000. Our records show that CERL members executed only a very small number of searches on this database, so we trust that any inconvenience caused will be minimal.

Since 1997, RLG has offered CERL members access to the Blackwell's Table of Contents file at no additional charge. When the contract between RLG and Blackwell's for this file came due for renewal, Blackwell's price increase was so substantial that continuing access was not feasible. Note that RLG will continue the weekly loading of Blackwell's Enhanced LC-CIP records into the RLG union catalogue under the Library Identifier XBCP.

New committee members and new CERL members

We welcome CERL's new Director and members of the Executive Committee and our new CERL members:

New Director:

At the CERL Full Members' meeting Dr H. Leskien, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, stepped down at the end of his term of office. He was not available for re-election.

- François Dupuigrenet-Desroussilles, ENSSIB, Lyon
- Dr E. Mittler was re-elected and will continue to act as Treasurer

New members of the Executive Committee:

- Dr Fernanda Campos, Biblioteca Nacional, Lisbon, Portugal
 - Dr Olga Koulish, National Library of Russia, St Petersburg, Russia
 - Dr Margherita Spinazzola, Soprintendenza per i beni librari, Bologna, Italy
- They take the places of F. Dupuigrenet-Desroussilles, A. Matheson and I. Tsvetkova.

New CERL members:

- Bibliothèque municipale, Lyon (Full Member)
- National Szechenyi Library, Budapest (Full Member)
- Museum Plantin-Moretus, Antwerp (Special Member)

A full and up to date list of committee members and CERL members may be found on

<http://www.cerl.org/cerl~org.htm>.

All best wishes for 2001

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